

Reaction of *p*-Toluenesulphonyl Chloride with Some Dihalogeno-dinitrophenols

D. S. Deorha, H. L. Sharma, and V. K. Mahesh

3,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitro-, 2-chloro-3-bromo-4,6-dinitro-, 2,3-dibromo-4,6-dinitro-, and 2,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-phenols have been prepared and their behaviours with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in presence of diethylaniline studied.

Although the action of *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride on suitably substituted dinitrophenols in presence of diethylaniline provides one of the methods^{1,2} of replacing a hydroxyl group by a chlorine atom, this method does not appear to have been much studied; reference could be found³ in literature for only a few of them. During the present investigation, 3,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro-(I), 2-chloro-3-bromo-4,6-dinitro-(II), 2,3-dibromo-4,6-dinitro-(III), and 2,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitrophenols (IV) have been prepared and their reaction with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride has been studied.

Compounds (II) and (III) were obtained by halogenating 3-bromo-4,6-dinitrophenol⁴ with sulphuryl chloride and bromine respectively. Chlorination of 3-chloro-4,6-dinitrophenol⁴ with sulphuryl chloride or the dinitration of 2,3-dichlorophenol⁵ afforded the dinitrophenol (IV).

To obtain (I), 1,3,4-trichloro-2,6-dinitrobenzene⁶ was heated with sodium acetate and acetamide⁷. As the trihalogeno-dinitrobenzene has two activated chlorine atoms, the product could be (I) or 3,6-dichloro-2,4-dinitrophenol according as the chlorine at position 1 or 3 in 1,3,4-trichloro-2,6-dinitrobenzene is replaced. As both the 1,3,4-trichloro-2,6-dinitro-(A) and 3,4-dichloro-1-bromo-2,6-dinitrobenzenes (B)⁶ under the similar reaction condition provide the same monohydric phenol, its structure can only be (I). This was found to be identical with the product obtained by dinitration of 3,4-dichlorophenol⁵.

1. Ullmann *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1870; 1910, 43, 3939; 1911, 44, 37.
2. Sane *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2481; this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 299; 1932, 9, 55, 59; 1933, 10, 459.
3. Korner, *Gazetta*, 1874, 4, 400.
4. Titov and Laptév, *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1949, 19, 287; Hodgson and Moore, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1601.
5. Hollemann, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1917, 37, 96.
6. Joshi and Gupta, this *Journal*, 1952, 28, 193.
7. Borsche *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1339.

The substituted phenols (II, III, and IV) on reaction with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride in presence of diethylaniline yielded 1,2-dichloro-3-bromo-4,6-dinitro-, 1-chloro-2,3-dibromo-4,6-dinitro-, and 1,2,3-trichloro-4,6-dinitro-benzene respectively. These trihalogeno derivatives have been characterised by preparing a few derivatives with aniline, *p*-toluidine, and piperidine (Tables II and III).

The phenol (I) under similar conditions of reaction yielded neither the 1,3,4-trichloro-2,6-dinitrobenzene nor the *p*-toluenesulphonate. The reason for this behaviour is not clear. This phenol has been characterised by preparing its acetyl and benzoyl derivatives.

EXPERIMENTAL

3,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitrophenol (I).—(i). A mixture of 1,3,4-trichloro-2,6-dinitrobenzene⁵ (5 g.), sodium acetate (5 g.), and acetamide (15 g.) was heated at 160° for an hour. The melt was dissolved in strong ammonium hydroxide (75 ml). The solution was heated with activated charcoal (0.5 g.) on a water bath for 2 hours. Acidification of the filtrate afforded the dichlorodinitrophenol which crystallised from ethanol in yellow crystals, m.p. 168°. (Found: Cl, 27.91. $C_6H_2O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 28.06%).

(ii). Similarly, 3,4-dichloro-1-bromo-2,6-dinitrobenzene⁶ yielded the same phenol; m.p. 168° (mixed m.p. with the above remained undepressed).

(iii). 3,4-Dichlorophenol⁵ (8 g.), dissolved in acetic acid (25 ml), was treated with HNO_3 (conc., 12 ml) dropwise with shaking and the temperature was not allowed to rise above 40°. After keeping overnight, it was heated on a water bath till nitrous fumes had ceased to evolve. Dilution with water provided dichlorodinitrophenol which crystallised from ethanol in yellow crystals, m.p. 168°.

The acetyl derivative crystallised from ethanol in yellow crystals, m.p. 128°, (Found: Cl, 23.88. $C_8H_4O_6N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 24.06%).

The benzoyl derivative crystallised from ethanol in yellow prisms, m.p. 147°. (Found: Cl, 19.59. $C_{13}H_8O_6N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 19.88%).

2-Chloro-3-bromo-4,6-dinitrophenol (II).—To a solution of 3-bromo-4,6-dinitrophenol⁹ (10.4 g.) in acetic acid (40 ml) was added sulphuryl chloride (3.6 ml). After keeping the mixture overnight, it was diluted with ice-cold water. The precipitate was crystallised from methanol in yellow prisms, m.p. 118°. (Found: N, 9.58. $C_6H_3O_2N_2BrCl$ requires N, 9.41%).

2,3-Dibromo-4,6-dinitrophenol (III).—Bromine (2.2 ml), dissolved in acetic acid (20 ml), was added to a solution of 3-bromo-4,6-dinitrophenol (10.4 g.) in the same solvent (40 ml) dropwise. The reaction mixture was warmed at 60° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and then poured on ice when bromodinitrophenol separated in light yellow prism, m.p. 122°. (Found: N, 8.36. $C_6H_2O_2N_2Br_2$ requires N, 8.18%).

2,3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitrophenol (IV).—(i). This was obtained by chlorinating 3-chloro-4,6-dinitrophenol with sulphuryl chloride by following the procedure described under (II). The product crystallised from methanol in light yellow prisms, m.p. 114°. (Found: N, 10.91. $C_6H_2O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires N, 11.06%).

(ii). 2,3-Dichlorophenol⁵ on dinitration by following the procedure, described under (I). afforded the phenol (IV); m.p. and mixed m.p. 114°.

Reaction of the Phenols with p-Toluenesulphonyl Chloride.—A mixture of a dihalogeno-dinitrophenol (0.012 *M*), *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (0.022 *M*), and diethylaniline (15 ml) was heated on a boiling water bath for 4 hours. From the dark mixture, diethylaniline was removed by HCl (dil.) and unchanged phenol by aqueous sodium carbonate. The residue was dissolved in ethanol and the solution boiled with animal charcoal. From the filtered and concentrated solution, trihalogeno-dinitrobenzene separated. The characteristics of the trihalogeno-dinitrobenzenes obtained by this method are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Substituted phenol used.	Halonitrobenzene formed.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
I	*	Nli	..	..	..	..	..
II	1,2-Dichloro-3-bromo-4,6-D	50%	118°	Light yellow	C ₆ HO ₂ N ₂ BrCl ₂	8.79	8.96
III	1-Chloro-2,3-dibromo-4,6-D	55	133°	Do	C ₆ HO ₂ N ₂ Br ₂ Cl	7.87	7.76
IV	1,2,3-Trichloro-4,6-D	48	99°	Colorless	C ₆ HO ₂ N ₂ Cl ₃	10.48	10.31

*OH was not replaced by Cl.
D = dinitrobenzene.

TABLE II

Derivatives of 1-chloro-2,3-dibromo-4,6-dinitrobenzene.

Amine used.	Derivative formed.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Bromine.	
					Found.	Reqd.
Aniline	2-Bromo-1,3-dianilino-4,6-D	198°	Orange	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ Br	18.45	18.64
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	2-Bromo-1,3-di- <i>p</i> -toluidino-4,6-D	175°	Orange-red	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₄ Br	17.36	17.50
Piperidine	2-Bromo-1,3-dipiperidino-4,6-D	176°	Dull orange	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₄ Br	19.19	19.37

D = dinitrobenzene.

TABLE III

Derivatives of 1,2-dichloro-3-bromo- and 1,2,3-trichloro-4,6-dinitrobenzenes.

Amine used.	Derivative formed.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Chlorine.	
					Found.	Reqd.
Aniline	2-Chloro-1,3-dianilino-4,6-D	187.88°	Bright orange	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	9.06	9.23
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	2-Chloro-1,3-di- <i>p</i> -toluidino-4,6-D	219°	Dull ..	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	8.49	8.60
Piperidine	2-Chloro-1,3-dipiperidino-4,6-D	197°	Orange	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	9.88	9.93

D = dinitrobenzene.

Reaction with Amines.—An ethanolic solution of a trihalogeno-dinitrobenzene was refluxed with 2 moles of an amine in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate for 2 hours. The product was crystallised from ethanol (Tables II and III). The halogen atoms at 1 and 3 positions, activated by the nitro groups, are substituted.

SCHOOL OF CHEMISTRY
MEERUT COLLEGE, MEERUT.
AND
DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF RAJASTHAN,
JAIPUR.

Received June 4, 1962.